

Table 2. Mean performance of CMS lines for some agronomic characters.^a Western Uttar Pradesh, India, 1990 WS.

CMS line	Days to 50% flowering		Plant height (cm)		Tillers (no.)		Panicle length (cm)		Pollen fertility (%)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)		Fertile spikelets (%)		
	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	A	B	Unbagged		Bagged
												A	B	A
IR46829	105.0	96.0	81.3	94.8	7.3	13.3	20.0	21.8	0.0	117.2	102.3	0.0	70.5	0.0
IR54752	118.0	117.0	102.0	104.8	10.3	11.4	25.2	28.3	10.3	191.6	194.5	20.0	48.2	18.5
IR54753	117.0	109.0	120.0	110.5	9.0	11.1	27.6	28.0	31.0	164.1	219.5	39.9	57.4	30.2
IR54754	110.0	101.0	90.3	98.0	9.8	11.0	23.8	25.6	0.0	189.9	163.7	2.7	63.8	0.0
IR54758	109.0	106.0	100.5	110.8	9.6	8.2	22.2	26.6	0.0	186.0	180.9	11.4	57.7	0.0
Pragathi	109.0	102.0	105.4	98.7	7.7	10.8	26.3	24.7	43.6	217.6	151.4	23.3	50.5	20.5
Pushpa	121.0	115.5	97.4	104.5	9.7	12.7	27.7	29.0	46.8	217.6	201.1	40.8	51.7	35.6
V20	76.0	69.0	75.0	81.1	22.2	9.0	21.1	2.1	0.0	128.3	93.2	17.7	72.8	0.0
Mean	108.2	102.0	96.6	100.4	10.7	10.9	24.2	25.7	16.4	176.3	163.2	19.5	59.2	13.1
LSD (0.05)	5.5	4.1	12.1	3.5	7.0	6.6	3.5	2.3	13.4	57.6	35.0	10.4	12.9	13.2
LSD (0.01)	8.2	6.0	17.9	5.1	10.3	9.7	5.3	3.4	19.9	85.1	51.7	15.4	19.1	18.6

^aA = CMS line, B = maintainer of CMS line (A).

Using potassium chlorate (KClO₃) to distinguish indica-japonica hybrids from indica and japonica parents

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Phenol reaction of the hull can be used to distinguish indica from japonica varieties but not indica-japonica hybrids from their parents because the hybrids show a positive reaction as indicas. We tested whether the multigenic inheritance for KClO₃ tolerance in rice seedlings can be used to distinguish indica-japonica hybrids from their parents.

We soaked 100 seedlings with plumules of 0.5-1.0 cm for each of six indica-japonica hybrids (F₁) and their parents in 1% KClO₃ solution for 24 h, then washed and stored them at 30 °C for 4-5 d. The experiment was replicated twice. Degree of KClO₃ injury for each seedling was scored on a scale of 0-3 (see table). Percentage of seedlings injured was estimated using injury index:

$$\text{Injury index} = \frac{\sum (\text{score} \times \text{seedling no.})}{\text{the largest score} \times \text{total seedling no.}}$$

Reaction score and injury index of hybrid and parent rice seedlings after KClO₃ treatment.

Hybrid or parent	Seedlings (no.)	Seedlings (no.) with given reaction score ^a				Injury index ^b (%)
		0	1	2	3	
<i>Indica</i>						
CE 64	203			53	150	91.3 a
Xiangai	200			74	126	87.7 a
Ks-9	200			27	173	95.5 a
w6154s	208			118	90	81.1 a
<i>Hybrid</i>						
Ce 64/02428	201		110	83	8	45.7 b
Xiangai/02428	197		159	33	5	40.6 b
Ks-9/029	208		117	91	3	49.4 b
w6154s/02428	200		156	39	5	41.5 b
w6154s/029	198		130	67	1	44.9 b
Ce 64/029	205		145	56	4	45.7 b
<i>Japonica</i>						
02428	200	200				0 c
029	200	200				0 c

^a0 = normal growth without any injury, 1 = partial chlorosis at the margin of the first euphyllum, 2 = yellowing with partial rolling of the first euphyllum, 3 = withering of whole seedling. ^bIn a column, values followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 1% level.

Analysis of variance with a complete random design was used to test for significant differences.

The three seedling types differed distinctly in their tolerance for KClO₃.

Japonica parents were tolerant of KClO₃ and indica parents sensitive. Most of the hybrids reacted moderately, giving an injury index (40-50%) intermediate

between their indica and japonica parents.

Results suggest that tolerance of seedlings for KClO₃ can be used to test whether the type is a true hybrid or a pure indica or japonica. ■